

Relationship Between Personality Traits and Perceived Job Performance of Secondary School Teachers in Adamawa State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the relationship between personality traits and perceived job performance of secondary school teachers in Adamawa State, Nigeria. Three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. Correlational survey research design was adopted for the study. The population was 6071 teachers. Total samples of 624 teachers were sampled for the study. The study employed the multistage sampling procedure. The instruments used for data collection were the Big Five Personality Inventory of Personality Traits (BFPT) and Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ). The instruments were validated by experts from the Department of Environmental and Life Sciences Education. The reliability of the instruments was tested using Cronbach Alpha statistic. The reliability coefficients obtained were 0.79 for BFPT and 0.80 for TJPQ. The findings of the study revealed that teachers demonstrated high levels of: conscientiousness personality trait (grand mean of 4.26), and agreeableness personality trait (grand mean of 3.98). There is a significant positive relationship between openness to experience personality trait and perceived job performance of teachers in secondary schools in Adamawa state ($r = 0.78, p = 0.00 < 0.05$), There is significant positive relationship between conscientiousness personality trait and perceived job performance of teachers in secondary schools in Adamawa state ($r = 0.68, p = 0.00 < 0.05$). There is a strong and positive significant relationship between agreeableness personality trait and perceived job performance of teachers in secondary schools in Adamawa state ($r = 0.81, p = 0.00 < 0.05$). Lastly, there is a strong and positive relationship between personality traits and perceived job performance of teachers in secondary schools in Adamawa State ($r = 0.74, R^2 = 55\%, F(5, 618) = 151.27, p = 0.00 < 0.05$). The study concluded that personality traits have relationship with teacher's job performance in public secondary schools in Adamawa State. Based on these findings, it was recommended that government should make it a policy matter to evaluate teachers' personality traits on quarterly basis to improve effective administration and job performance in secondary schools. Authorities concerned should assess the personality traits of teachers while promoting them to the rank of principals.

Keywords: personality traits, conscientiousness, agreeableness, openness, job performance.

Introduction

Personality can be described as the characteristics of, or how someone acts in certain way. Hence, from the good personality of teacher, they can perform the job well, easily communicate with other team members and cooperate or give hand for each other in completing specific task through understanding the concept of big five model. The Big Five Model is one of the most highly regarded trait theories of personality in which variations of personality are explained by five orthogonal factors, namely; openness to experience, emotional stability (or neurotism), extraversion, agreeableness and conscientiousness, and (Saucier & Goldberg, 2002). The Big Five model developed by Costa and McCrae (1992) has emerged as a popular tool for understanding the relationship between personality traits and perceived job performance of teachers' (Poropat, 2009). It has been employed by many researchers (Mount, Witt, & Barrick, 2000; Harris, & Mowen, 2001; Sawyerr, Srinivas, & Wang, 2009). The "five factors" are openness to experience, neurotism, extraversion, agreeableness and conscientiousness.

The conscientiousness character of a person indicates the capacity to be responsible, achievement-striving, dependable, efficient, organized, hardworking and persevering. Agreeableness refers to the tendency to be sympathetic, helpful, friendly, tolerant, trusting, good natured, courteous and cooperative. An extraverted person is understood to be ambitious, reward-seeking, gregarious, sociable, adventurous and assertive. Emotional stability refers to the ability to remain calm, resilient, even-tempered, tolerant of stress, well-adjusted and self-confident. Finally, openness to experience indicates the capacity of a person to be broad-minded, imaginative, perceptive, intelligent, creative, curious and cultured. Conscientiousness personality trait is the most predictive of teachers' job performance (Hurtz & Donovan, 2000). Conscientiousness is a competence, order, dutifulness, achievement striving and self-discipline, the teachers recognizes the importance of reaching a goal and expends energetic, long-suffering and untiring efforts to obtain satisfaction from performing the duty effectively (Burch & Anderson, 2004). Conscientious teacher has also been found to adopt proactive self-initiative and creative thinking in solving problems. More so, such a teacher is goal oriented and will stop at nothing to achieve the desired results (Bakker, Van Der Zee, Lewig & Dollard, 2006). Thus, it can be concluded that, a conscientious employee is largely consistent, adventurous and reliable at the work place.

According to Barrick (2000), openness to experience is a tendency where an individual is very accommodating, adventurous, patient, dynamic and sincere in the performance of job roles and discharge of duties and responsibility. Principals identified with open to experience trait is mostly found to use humor as a stress coping mechanism and tend to appraise stressful situations as less threatening (Barrick 2000). Thus, such a teacher is very accommodating, adventurous, patient, dynamic and sincere in the performance of job roles and discharge of duties and responsibility. Mark and John (2000) analyzed the relationship between openness to experience and job performance and found that openness as a trait predicted unique variance in job performance for teachers beyond both cognitive aptitudes. Furthermore, teachers that are more open to experience may handle and solve problems positively.

Agreeableness describes one who is sympathetic, trusting and cooperative. Individuals with high level of agreeableness are selfless, flexible and pleasant. Such individuals work with others easily with little or no friction. Those with low level of this trait however, find it difficult going with others. McCrae and Costa in Daminabo (2008) noted this to be psychotics, which refer to a person who is skeptical, unsympathetic, uncooperative and rude. Teachers with high level of agreeableness are said to have significant positive predictors of teachers' relationships. It is a tendency to be altruistic, cooperative, compliant, caring and warm. It is because principals with compliance and dependence aspects of agreeableness are likely to cause teachers to perceived contractual obligations to stay with the organization (Colquitt & Le-Pine, 2009). Teachers with high agreeableness have value affiliation and avoid conflict at workplace. They are concerned for their jobs at schools and they are likely to be concerned with growth and development needs and are likely to be sure that teachers' job performance increase (Judge & Bono, 2002). More so, there is some evidence that agreeableness is linked to high levels of social support (Barrick, 2000).

According to Paunonen and Ashton (2001), the Big five personality dimensions of openness to experience, neurotism, extraversion, agreeableness and conscientiousness have been associated with a variety of work attitudes and behavior. These five personality dimensions are broad dimensions that are theorized to subsume most narrowly focused personality traits. The breadth of these dimensions is a benefit in that it distills a large number of personality traits into a parsimonious set of dimensions for use in research. It means that this model is widely used and suitable to use in any research. As stated by Harris and Mowen (2001), the Five Factor Model has enjoyed widespread popularity in the field. Five personality traits collectively classify the higher-level dispositions of an individual according to the Five Factor Model.

Job performance refers to "the overall expected value from teachers' behaviour carried out over the course of a set period of time". This connotes that job performance involves what the staff of a giving school do at the school, which is aimed at either improving the educational goal or otherwise. It implies that the staff behaviour and general activities is measured by a giving standard to assess the staff activities in the school (Wilson, 2017). According to Magno and Sembrano (2008), teacher job performance includes measures of general teaching practices such as teaching methods and strategies, classroom management, planning and organization of teaching. Neubert and Taggar (2004) argued that the relationship between job performance and the Big Five personality dimensions are more of a consequence of social aspects of the workplace than ability. It means that the school should increase the positive impressions of the teachers towards them. The behavioral pattern of a good principal such as full cooperation, supports, and speaks favorably could exceed the teachers' job performance (Neubert and Taggar, 2004).

Job performance is one of the significant relationships with the goals of organization that most of the organizations need to focus on. Job performance has been investigated as the light of work like attitudes in performing job, job satisfaction and their commitment in completing the task (Fatheya-Mahmood, 2008). Teachers' job performance was found to have positive relationship with the Big Five personality traits (Barrick, & Mount, 2000). Griffin (2005) explained that the performance of an individual is determined by three factors i.e. motivation, work environment and ability to do work. Chandrasekar (2011) examined that the school environment impacts on teachers' morale, productivity and job performance both positively and negatively. If the school environment is not favourable to the teachers, they maybe de-

motivated and their performance may also be affected. Poorly designed work timings, poor scheduling of duties, lack of appreciation, and lack of personal decision making opportunity may be some of the contributors to ineffective teachers' job performance in senior secondary schools of Adamawa State. One of the prominent trends in schools today is the attention placed on individual personality traits as a means of correlates of job performance (Engler, 2006).

Since the National Policy on Education by the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN. 2013) states that no education system will rise above the quality of its teachers, and the implementation of the school's curriculum revolves around the teacher, there is the need to assess the relationship between teachers' personality traits and their perceived job performance at secondary schools level in Adamawa state. The study of teacher's personality traits and their perceived job performance in secondary schools in Adamawa State may help improve the overall outputs of secondary schools in Adamawa State.

Statement of the Problem

Studies show a consistent fall in teachers' job performance in Nigeria and Adamawa state in particular, which further translates to students' underachievement. Different factors such as teacher attitude, relationship with other colleagues, level of educational attainment and environment may influence teachers' job performance in secondary schools of Adamawa state. Despite the useful insights these factors have contributed to our understanding of factors responsible for teachers' job performance, our knowledge is still inadequate on the relationship between teacher's personality traits and their perceived job performance. Significance progress awaits studies that can be conducted to address these issues as considerable studies show teachers play a vital role. They are instrumental in controlling schools to achieve its goals. Teachers have different interests, abilities and special personality characteristics. This may reflect in their performance in schools. As Gurr & Mulford. (2005) stated; teachers personality characteristics enhances students' efficacy in schools. No education system (and a country) will successfully thrive without good and quality teachers. This means that the success of any nation hinged on her education system which heavily relies on the success or failure of its teachers. Therefore, in order to motivate teachers to effectively perform their duties, it is necessary to develop valid selection criteria for identifying successful teachers and the characteristics of such teachers need to be studied. It is based on this rationale that the study investigated the relationship between personality traits and perceived job performance of teachers in secondary schools in Adamawa state, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to investigate the relationship between personality trait of teachers' and their perceived job performance in secondary schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to determine:

1. The relationship between teacher's openness to experience and their job performance in secondary schools in Adamawa state.
2. The relationship between teachers' conscientiousness and their job performance in secondary schools in Adamawa state?
3. The relationship between teachers' agreeableness and their job performance in secondary schools in Adamawa state.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study;

1. What is the level of teachers' openness to experience in secondary schools in Adamawa state?
2. What is the level of teachers' conscientiousness in secondary schools in Adamawa state?
3. What is the level of teachers' agreeableness in secondary schools in Adamawa state?

1.5 Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance to guide the study:

H0₁: There is no significant relationship between teachers' openness to experience and their perceived job performance in public secondary schools in Adamawa state.

H0₂: There is no significant relationship between teacher's conscientiousness and their perceived job performance in secondary schools in Adamawa state.

H0₃: There is no significant relationship between teacher's agreeableness and their perceived job performance in secondary schools in Adamawa state.

Methodology

Area of the Study

The area of the study is Adamawa State located in the North Eastern part of Nigeria; it is bordered by Borno and Yobe states in the North, Gombe state in the west, Taraba state in the south and the Republic of Cameroun from the east. It lies between latitude 8°N and 11°N and longitude 11.5° E and 13.5°E. The state covers a land mass of 39,742.12 square kilometers that is about 4.4% of the land area of Nigeria. It has a population of 3,168,101 based on the 2006 census. The state has five education zones; Mubi zone with 76 senior secondary schools, Gombi zone with 55 senior secondary

schools, Yola zone with 93 senior secondary schools, Ganye zone with 52 senior secondary schools and Numan zone with 61 senior secondary schools (Adamawa State Post Primary Schools Management Board, 2016), 21 Local Government areas and 337 senior secondary schools (Adamawa State Post Primary Schools Management Board, 2016). The state was chosen for this study because it is one of the educationally backward states in Northeast Nigeria. A study as such helps to uncover the problems that might have been bedeviling education in the state.

Research Design

This study adopted a correlational survey research design. According to Nworgu (2006) correlational survey design is a design that seeks to know what relationship exists between two or more variables. Usually, such studies indicate the direction and magnitude of the relationship between the variables. Correlational research is concerned with establishing relationships between two or more variables in the same population or between the same variables in two populations (Leedy & Ormrod, 2010). A correlational study determines whether or not two variables are correlated. This means to study whether an increase or decrease in one variable corresponds to an increase or decrease in the other variable (Cohen, 1988). The researcher considered this design appropriate for this study to investigate relationship between and among variables of personality traits and teachers job performance in secondary schools of Adamawa State. The choice of this research design is also due to the fact that the set of data from the group used in the study (Teachers) comes from a normal population distribution. Samples are independent and randomly selected to enable the researcher determine which personality trait correlate with teachers' job performance.

Population

The population of the study consists of all teachers in senior secondary school in the five educational zones in Adamawa State, Nigeria. According to Post Primary Schools Management Board, Yola, Adamawa State, as at June, 2019, the population of teachers was 6071 in all the five education zones, in Adamawa State across the 21 local government areas of the State.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sample for this study consisted of 624 respondents made up of teachers. A multistage sampling procedure was adopted for this study. In the first stage, the cluster sampling technique was used in selecting three education zones for the study. In the second stage, two Local Government Areas were selected from each of the three educational zones which make up six LGAs, using simple random sampling technique. Simple random sampling technique was also used to give every Local Government Area equal chance of being selected for the study. The names of the Local Governments were written on pieces of papers, folded and put in a container, shuffled and the researcher drew the local Government Areas with replacement (i.e. balloting with replacement).

At the third stage, four senior secondary schools from each of the six LGAs were selected which made up of 24 schools selected using simple random sampling involving the use of balloting with replacement. At the fourth stage, the simple random sampling technique was to select 13 teachers from each of the senior secondary schools. This means that, in each of the 24 schools, 13 teachers (male and female) were selected to give a total of 624 teachers involved in the study. The sampling procedure covered more grounds. More so, since the statistical tool used for this study (Pearson's correlation) can only correlate between matching sets of responses from respondents, necessitated this selection technique (balloting with replacement). Thereafter, the Cochran's (1963) sample size formula (with correction for finite population) viz: $n = \frac{z^2 * p * (1 - p) / e^2}{1 + (z^2 * p * (1 - p) / (e^2 * N))}$ where: n = sample size, z = z score associated with a level of confidence, p = sample proportion (expressed as a decimal), e = margin of error (expressed as a decimal), N = population was used to derive these samples.

Instruments for Data Collection

Instruments used in this study are the Teachers Big Five Personality Inventory (TBFPTPQ) and Job Performance Questionnaire. The instruments were adapted versions of Big Five Inventory and Teachers' Performance Inventory of Bennell and Akyeampong (2007); Rammstedt and John (2007). The big five personality inventory is a 50-item scale which assesses the five personality traits (openness to experience, extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness and neuroticism) of Teachers. The respondents gave his/her rating for each of the items with 5-point modified Likert type rating ranging from Very High Level (5), High Level (4), Moderate Level (3), Low Level (2) to Very Low Level (1).

Also, section B measured job performance. The section consisted of 20 items which elicits information on the job performance in terms of lesson note preparation, effective teaching, class control, and use of teaching materials, method of teaching, class participation and evaluation of teaching. The response mode is similar to the modified 5-point Likert scale type: Very High Level (5), High Level (4), Moderate Level (3), Low Level (2) to Very Low Level (1).

Method of Data Collection

A letter of introduction was collected to facilitate compliance of participants in the study. The researcher designed an instrument tagged Teachers Big Five Inventory Job Performance Questionnaire (TBFJPQ) to collect data. Permission was sought from the 24 senior secondary schools involved in this study. In order to enhance the speed of distributing the instruments for the study the researcher employed two Research Assistants resident in two education zones, while the researcher handled one education zone. The Research Assistants through the help of the Senior Masters in each of the secondary schools visited distributed the TBFJPQ to the teachers in order to determine the personality traits and teachers' job performance. It should be noted that more schools (288) were later considered in the distribution of the Big Five Inventory of Teacher (BFITJPQ). However, the 624 Teachers in those schools were later approached by the researcher and the two Research Assistants at one of their meetings of All Nigerian Conference of Teachers of Secondary Schools (ANCOPSS) conducted in FCE, Yola in December, 2025. The inventory was issued to them after seeking the permission from the chairman of the occasion. They filled the inventory and returned it instantaneously. Teachers were instructed on how to answer and return the completed questionnaires. The method of distribution of instruments was carefully done to ensure 100% return rate. Furthermore, the questionnaire and achievement test were counted by each Research Assistant before distribution to ensure balance on retrieval. This is to further ensure balance for correlating the data. After collection of the instruments from the teachers by the Research Assistants, the researcher subjected the data to further statistical analysis.

Method for Data Analysis

Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions One to Six using the real limits of numbers for remark. The remark for research questions are: Very High Level (VHL) with 4.5-5.00 real limits, High Level (HL) with 3.50-4.49 real limits, Moderate Level (ML) with 2.50-3.49 real limit, Low Level (LL) with 1.50-2.49 real limit, Very Low Level; (VLL) with 0.50-1.49 real limit. The Pearson product moment correlation statistics was used for testing null hypotheses One to Five while, multiple linear regression was used for testing null hypothesis six at 0.05 level of significance. All data will be analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 23. All data will be analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 23. Furthermore, $r = +1$ or -1 shows a positive or negative relationship respectively. The strength of the correlation was defined by: when $r = 0.10$ to 0.29 , the relationship is positively low, $r = 0.30$ to 0.49 shows a positively moderate relationship and $r = 0.50$ to 1.0 shows a positively strong relationship (Cohen, 1988).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question One: What is the level of Teachers openness to experience in secondary schools in Adamawa state? The response to each item by the 624 teachers on their openness to experience constituted the data. Furthermore, descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were employed to answer this research question. The result is illustrated in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of Descriptive Statistics of Mean and Standard Deviation of Teachers Openness to Experience

S/no.	Item = 624	Mean	SD	Remark
I see myself as someone who...				
31.	Comes up with new ideas.	3.95	0.77	HL
32.	Has an active imagination	4.06	0.81	HL
33.	Values artistic.	4.00	0.72	HL
34.	Likes to reflect.	4.22	0.77	HL
35.	Is sophisticated in art.	4.29	1.11	HL
36.	Prefers work that is routine.	3.49	0.91	HL
37.	Is curious about many different things.	4.67	0.81	HL
38.	Is inventive.	4.64	0.63	HL
39.	Play with ideas.	4.76	0.51	HL
40.	Has minimal artistic interests.	4.78	0.49	HL
Grand mean		4.29		HL

As demonstrated in Table 1, the teachers' response (items 31-40) to openness to experience is high. Furthermore, the grand mean of 4.29 indicated that teachers demonstrated high level of openness to experience in secondary schools.

Research Question Two: What is the level of teachers' conscientiousness in public secondary schools in Adamawa state?

Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used to answer this research question. It should be noted that each item on teachers' conscientiousness contains 624 mean responses of the teachers to the item. Table 2 illustrates the result.

Table 2: Summary of Descriptive Statistics of Mean and Standard Deviation of Teachers Conscientiousness personality traits

S/no.	Item	n = 624	Mean	SD	Remark
I see myself as someone who...					
41.	Does a thorough job.		4.32	0.74	HL
42.	Can be somewhat careless.		4.36	0.80	HL
43.	Is a reliable worker.		4.05	0.99	HL
44.	Tends to be disorganized.		4.27	0.85	HL
45.	Tends to be lazy.		4.32	0.79	HL
46.	Perseveres until the task is finished.		4.18	0.92	HL
47.	Does things efficiently.		4.28	0.90	HL
48.	Is easily distracted.		4.25	0.85	HL
49.	Follows through with plans.		4.33	0.78	HL
50.	Is energetic.		4.21	0.87	HL
Grand mean			4.26		HL

Table 2 reveals that teachers responded high to items 41-50 which centered on principals' conscientiousness. Going by the grand mean of 4.26, it could be said that the teachers demonstrated high level of conscientiousness in public secondary schools.

Research Question Three: What is the level of teachers' agreeableness secondary schools in Adamawa state?

The data for answering this question was obtained from teachers responses on agreeableness as a personality trait. The research question was then answered using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation. Table 3 presents the result.

Table 3: Summary of Descriptive Statistics of Mean and Standard Deviations of Teachers' Agreeableness Personality Trait

S/no.	Item	n = 312	Mean	SD	Remark
I see myself as someone who...					
51.	Tends to find fault with others.		4.34	0.96	HL
52.	Unselfish with others.		4.83	0.53	VHL
53.	Starts quarrels with others.		4.86	0.53	VHL
54.	Has a forgiving nature.		4.90	0.52	VHL
55.	Is generally trusting.		4.67	0.74	VHL
56.	Can be cold.		3.25	0.90	ML
57.	Kind to almost everyone.		3.21	0.98	ML
58.	Is sometimes rude to others.		3.02	1.02	ML
59.	Likes to cooperate with others.		3.42	0.91	ML
60.	Makes people to feel at ease.		3.28	0.98	ML
Grand mean			3.98		HL

Data in Table 3 on agreeableness personality trait indicates that the level of teacher's response was high on item 1; very high to items 2, 3, 4, 5, and moderate to items 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10. However, going by the grand mean of 3.98, it could be interpreted that teachers demonstrated high level of agreeableness personality trait.

Hypotheses Testing

H0₁: There is no significant relationship between principals' openness to experience and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Adamawa state.

This hypothesis was tested by correlating the mean responses of principals on openness to experience with that of the teachers on job performance. The statistical tool applied to analyze the data was Pearson product moment correlation statistic. The results are displayed in Table 4.

Table 4: Summary of PPMC Analysis of Relationship between Teachers Openness to Experience and Their perceived Job Performance

Variable	n	Mean	SD	r	p-value	Decision
Teachers Openness to Experience	624	4.29	0.75	0.78	.00*	Reject
Teachers' Job Performance	624	3.03	0.90			

*Significant; $p < 0.05$.

The summary of data on the relationship between openness to experience personality trait teachers' perceived job performance shows significant positive relationship on a high level. This means that the mean responses of openness to experience ($\bar{X} = 4.29$, $SD. = 0.75$) and that of teachers job performance ($\bar{X} = 3.03$, $SD. = 0.90$) correlates at $r = 0.78$, $p = 0.00$. This implies that as openness to experience improves, the teachers' job performance also improves. Hence, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship earlier stated is rejected.

H0₂: There is no significant relationship between teacher's conscientiousness and their perceived job performance in secondary schools in Adamawa state.

The 624 teachers mean responses on conscientiousness on the X column with the 624 mean responses on their job performance on the Y column were correlated using Pearson product moment correlation method in SPSS version 23. Table 5 displays the data.

Table 5: Summary of PPMC Analysis of Relationship between Teachers Conscientiousness and Their perceived Job Performance

Variable	n	Mean	SD	r	p-value	Decision
Conscientiousness	624	4.26	0.85	0.68	.00*	Reject
Teachers' Job Performance	624	3.03	0.90			

*Significant; $p < 0.05$.

The result in Table 5 reveals a significant positive relationship between conscientiousness personality trait of teachers and their perceived job performance in secondary schools in Adamawa state ($r = 0.68$, $n = 624$, $p = 0.00 < 0.05$). This result means that improvement in teachers conscientiousness personality trait led to an improvement in their job performance. Hence, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship is hereby rejected.

H0₃: There is no significant relationship between teacher's agreeableness and their job performance in secondary schools in Adamawa state.

This hypothesis was tested by correlating the mean responses of teachers' agreeableness personality trait on the X column ($n = 624$) with the mean responses of their job performance on the Y column ($n = 624$). Through the use of SPSS version 23, the Pearson product moment correlation statistical tool was applied to analyze the data. The result is in Table 6.

Table 6: Summary of PPMC Analysis of Relationship between Teachers' Agreeableness and Their perceived Job Performance

Variable	n	Mean	SD.	r	p- value	Decision
Teachers Agreeableness	624	3.98	0.81	0.81	.00*	Reject
Teachers' Job Performance	624	3.03	0.90			

*Significant; $p < 0.05$.

The data in the Table 6 shows that the mean of teachers' agreeableness personality trait ($\bar{X} = 3.98$, SD. =0.81) significantly correlates with the mean of their job performance ($\bar{X} = 3.03$, SD. = 0.90) at $r = 0.81$, $p = 0.00$. This indicates a positive relationship between agreeableness personality trait of teachers' and their perceived job performance in secondary schools in Adamawa state. The relationship was strong meaning that a great improvement in Teachers agreeableness personality trait led to a corresponding improvement in their job performance. Hence, the null hypothesis which says, there is no significant relationship between agreeableness personality trait of teachers' and their perceived job performance in secondary schools in Adamawa state is here by rejected.

Discussions

This study found a high level of teacher's openness to experience in secondary schools of Adamawa State. Further to this, a significant positive relationship between openness to experience and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Adamawa state was also observed. This finding implies teachers that exhibit the traits curiosity, passion, willingness to learn and enthusiasm towards what they do positively influenced teachers' job performance. This finding is in line with Mark and John (2000), who analyzed the relationship between openness to experience and job performance and found that openness as a trait predicted unique variance in job performance for teachers beyond both cognitive aptitudes. However, Griffin (2004) found out that openness to experience is not a good predictor of job performance.

Yilmaz (2014) found that teachers' high level of openness to experience is very important in terms of educational organizations. A study found out that teachers identified with openness to experience trait are mostly found to use humor as a stress coping mechanism and tend to appraise stressful situations as less threatening (Bakker, 2006). Thus, such a teacher is very accommodating, adventurous, patient, dynamic and sincere in the performance of job roles and discharge of duties and responsibility. This study has reported a finding that further lends credence to the previous findings by Yilmaz (2014) and Bakker (2006).

The finding of this study shows that teachers in secondary schools of Adamawa State demonstrated high level of conscientiousness. Additionally, conscientiousness was found to be significantly positively related to teachers' job performance. A similar study has found that conscientiousness positively correlated with job performance (Hurtz & Donovan, 2000). Salgado (2003) buttresses this finding with a finding that showed a significant positive relationship between conscientiousness and teachers' job performance. However, Judge, Bono, Ilies, and Gerhardt (2002) found that some traits are negatively related to job performance.

Research have shown that individuals high on conscientiousness are meticulous, methodical, neat, well-organized, less impulsive, dedicated to their goals, reliable, trustworthy, and achievement striving (Roberts, Chernyshenko, Stark & Goldberg, 2005). Additionally, Costa and McCrae (2006) proved that people with high conscientiousness are purposeful, strong willed and determined. These could be the possible submission for the result obtained on conscientiousness.

This study indicated that teachers demonstrated high level of agreeableness personality trait. Furthermore, a significant positive relationship existed between agreeableness and teachers' job performance. It was observed that an improvement in agreeableness improves teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Adamawa state. Hashim, Rashid, Othman, Hamzah and Sunai (2012) found a significant relationship between agreeableness with job performance and Bhatti, Battour, Ismail and Sundram (2013) found out that individuals with agreeableness personality trait can maintain better work conditions to enhance job performance. These findings lend credence to the finding of this study. Nonetheless, Klang's (2012) study showed no correlation between agreeableness and job performance.

Empirical evidence from literature has shown that agreeableness is linked to high levels of social support (Bakker, 2006). Agreeable individual is generally considerate, kind, generous, trusting and trustworthy, helpful, and willing to compromise their interests with others (Rothmann, Coetzer, 2003). Even though Bartneck and Van der Hoek (2013) found out that sometimes their skepticism about others' motives causes them to be suspicious, unfriendly, and uncooperative, this study has discovered the high level of agreeability demonstrated by principles positively correlated with teachers' job performance in secondary school of Adamawa State.

Conclusion

The study concluded that personality trait has the capacity to influence teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Adamawa State. It was observed that the better the five personality traits considered in this study (openness to experience, conscientiousness and agreeableness), the better the job performance of teachers and vice-versa. Therefore, the employment of teachers should be done in line with critical assessment of personality traits of teachers by authorities concerned.

Recommendations

Considering the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made to enhance job performance of teachers in public secondary schools in Adamawa State:

1. Enlightenment campaign through seminars should be organized by the ministry of education to educate teachers who are very conservative or not open to other peoples' experience to develop this trait. Openness to experience could make the teachers to see things from other teachers' perspective. This will create a cordial working relationship and enhance job performance.
2. Teachers who are purposeful, strong willed and determined (conscientiousness) while delivering their duties should be the focus of the government. They should be given special treatments (incentives) to motivate others (teachers) to give in their best in supervising them to do their job.
3. Government should carry out training and retraining teachers to equip them with the necessary knowledge on agreeability, so that they can work together for peaceful co-existence. For it is said that, except the (teachers) agree, they cannot work together.

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